

Literature Review on the Relevance of Plants to the Nature of Human Health

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Abstract

Herbs are natural products, and the chemical composition of plants can evolve depending on several factors. Therefore, the chemical composition of herbs can vary from person to person, from the use of energetic decoctions to the use of herbal extracts according to the practices of Western and mainstream medicine. Traditional medicine has an exceptionally long history: it is a collection of practices based on the beliefs, beliefs and experiences of diverse cultures and times, often unexplained, and used to prevent as well as keep health. Traditional medicines can be traced back to magical or religious beliefs alongside folklore and experience, and the World Health Organization is working to develop definitive guidelines for clinical research methodology and evaluation of traditional medicine's efficacy. Traditional medical systems (TMS) have been the primary medical system in their country of origin for centuries. Despite the current dominance of the scientific medical model developed in the West, citizens and healthcare providers are beginning to trust and rely on TMS, which replaces traditional scientifically proven treatments with non-traditional ones. Overall, the cultural roots, longevity, and widespread use of TMS may show safety, but not the effectiveness of treatments. This is especially true of drugs having exceptionally low and exceptionally low concentrations of active substances, or the use of the sun, moon, etc. It applies to herbal medicines on which it is based on its magical-energetic properties. Traditional European herbalism uses categories like those found in traditional Asian medicine. These categories correspond to "humoral-energy theories" that describe properties (such as hot, cold, dry and moist) and elements (fire, air, water, earth, etc.). European folk medicine still recommends the use of so-called "depurative" herbs for the treatment of dermatological diseases such as psoriasis or eczema, as if these conditions were caused by poisoning. This recommendation

also includes diuretic herbs for arthritis, a decoction of stachys (also known as "fear grass") used as a bath to relieve fears, and straw baths for cancer treatment.

Keywords: *Herbs and healing, herbal medicines, herbal, herbal healing, natural healing*

1. Login

Although there are many distinctions between herbal and traditional pharmacological treatments, herbal medicines need to be evaluated for efficacy using traditional trial methodology . Several specific plant extracts have been proven effective for certain conditions. Herbal medicine has become a popular form of healthcare. Although the public is sometimes encouraged to assume that all natural remedies are basically safe, herbal remedies can have their dangers; therefore, research efforts in this area need to be increased. The primary question that is not satisfactorily answered concerns the triple absorption, metabolism and efficacy of plants and their extracts. This is a major unresolved problem in evaluating the many supposed beneficial effects that herbs and extracts have on human health.

Mind-body medicine can be considered a complementary or alternative mode to traditional Western medicine, and the various other modes of intervention currently used in a CAM paradigm can act largely through the mind-body connection ; and in that sense, reliance on traditional principles of a medicine deeply rooted in a culture may represent a kind of mind-body connection with real pharmacological activity through a placebo-like effect. Mind-body medicine can be considered an alternative or complementary mode. Consequently, successful therapy is often the result of both types of therapy working together in a synergistic manner; however, evaluation of the efficacy of traditional medicines is indistinguishable from that of mainstream medicine.

Long-term use of medicinal plants supplies a selection process, although short- and medium-term safe treatments are limited and only partial. However, this method does not meet current concerns about interactions caused by synthetic drugs. The treatment selection process is often limited, as the term "efficacy" may have different meanings in diverse cultures in relation to pathology and disease. For example, if a treatment is part of a TMS and the changes follow adaptation to local conditions and cultural practices, the transfer of a medical concept to a new country can be truly

illusory and lead to profound changes in its medical-therapeutic and cultural essence. . This is especially true if the changes are a result of the transfer. The extent to which these changes occur can vary greatly; however, it is possible for a TMS to internalize cultural elements from the host country within a few months or years following immigration.

2. Herbal Medicines

Herbal medicines are compounds that can be eaten or drunk and may be vitamins, minerals, herbs or parts thereof. Herbal remedies can be used to treat a variety of conditions. Herbs or parts of plants used for their perfume, aroma , or therapeutic properties are called aromatherapy herbs. Herbal medicines are unique from medicines in that they do not need to meet the pre-marketing safety and efficacy requirements that traditional medicines are needed to fulfill. This is one of the ways herbal medicines distinguish themselves from medicines. Many people are increasingly turning to the use of these products for the treatment of a wide variety of health problems in the context of health practices in various countries. The prevalence of use of herbal medicines has expanded dramatically all over the world.

have reported using herbal remedies to treat a wide variety of conditions , including disease prevention and treatment of long-term conditions such as dyslipidemia, hypertension, diabetes, cancer, and inflammatory bowel disorders .

Although the use of herbal medicines in various parts of the world differs according to geography, its frequency has been increasing in recent years. Similar proportions have been discovered throughout the Arab world. In Arab countries, about 80 percent of the population relies on herbal medicine for both disease prevention and treatment. For example, 37% of the population in Egypt reported using herbal medicines, while a much larger percentage (73%) of the population in Saudi Arabia used herbal medicines. Due to the combination of Jordan's historical, cultural and sociological influences, herbal medicines have managed to maintain their place in the local market. Traditional herbal medicines are used for a variety of reasons, including being inexpensive, closer to the patient's beliefs, avoiding concerns about the negative effects of chemical (synthetic) drugs,

and meeting the need for more personalized health care. and allows for a broader public approach to health information. Traditional herbal remedies are used to treat a variety of conditions, including :

It is assumed that as the number of adults using herbal medicine in Jordan increases, the number of cases where herbal medicines have harmful effects and interact with other herbal medicines will also increase. When health care practitioners are informed about the factors that predict herbal use, they can better find patients at elevated risk who may receive help from added counseling on the safe use of herbal medicines. This can supply avenues for easing positive social change by encouraging the development of stricter government policies to ensure consumer safety and promote high-quality products, as well as the development of public awareness interventions about herbal use and related health risks.

3. Coronavirus Example

Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (also known as SARS-CoV-2), also known as coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), had a tremendous impact on people's health all over the world. While the number of new cases is declining in a few countries that were hit particularly hard at the start of the epidemic, the number of new cases globally is rising steadily every day. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 2022b, as of March 25, 2022, COVID-19 infected more than 476 million people worldwide and managed approximately 6.1 million deaths. This pandemic has a wide clinical spectrum, from self-resolving respiratory diseases to fatal cases of pneumonia, but few effective treatments exist for it (Cao et al ., 2020).

As the first country hit hard by the COVID-19 pandemic, the Chinese government credits the integration of herbal medicine and traditional medicine for its rapid recovery in the management of COVID-19 (National Health Commission of the People's Republic of China, 2020; Weeks, 2020). China was the first country to be heavily affected by the COVID-19 outbreak. Many countries, including South Korea, Japan, Malaysia, and India, have also produced clinical practice guidelines or memorandums on herbal medicine use in response to COVID-19.

In the wake of the outbreak of COVID-19, many studies have been published, with several review articles, all of which present convincing data in favor of integrated herbal therapy. According to the findings of a recent comprehensive study, the combination of conventional therapy and traditional herbal medicine can reduce the symptoms of COVID-19 without increasing the risk of adverse drug reactions (Liu M. et al., 2020). However, the low quality of the technique used in clinical trials makes it difficult to draw any conclusions about the therapeutic benefits of herbal medicine. In yet another review article, the therapeutic evidence of herbal medicine integration in the management of COVID-19 symptoms was subjected to critical analysis and the authors note that herbal medicine has shown positive effects when combined with conventional medicine and has enormous potential to improve the treatment provided by traditional medicine (Chan et al., 2020).). However, data are inconclusive and more clinical research is needed to confirm this conclusion. Overall, research has shown that there is some degree of doubt about the efficacy of herbal medicine intervention for the treatment of COVID-19 and that extensive clinical trials are strongly needed.

Continuous monitoring of new evidence is needed to overcome the uncertainty in the evidence supporting the use of herbal medicines as an intervention in the treatment of COVID-19. This can be conducted using a technique known as live systematic review (LSR), in which a systematic review is continually revised to include new accessible material (Elliott et al., 2017). According to WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (ICTRP), more than one hundred randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of herbal medicine intervention have been registered worldwide and added trials are possible. the not- so -distant future [World Health Organization (WHO), 2022a]. As a result, new evidence is likely to appear that will enable informed decisions about the effectiveness of treatment using herbal remedies for the treatment of COVID-19 symptoms .

In this Literature Search and Review (LSR), an analysis of the evidence about the potential effects and risks of using herbal medicine for the treatment or prevention of COVID-19 has been made, with particular emphasis on the following questions:

- 1) *Is there evidence that herbal medicine can successfully treat COVID-19 patients?*

- 2) *Is there any evidence that herbal medicine can protect against COVID-19 infections ?*
- 3) *Does using herbal medicine to treat COVID-19 come with potential side effects or dangers that could go wrong?*

4. Comparisons with Other Studies and Reviews, Both in Agreement and in Conflict

A total of 21 systematic reviews were found to have findings comparable to this current review (Liu M. et al., 2020; Ang et al., 2020; Sun CY. et al., 2020; Xiong X. et al., 2020; Fan et al., 2020). ; Pang et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2020; Wang H. et al., 2021; Liu M. et al., 2021; Wang Q. et al., 2021; Du et al., 2021; Fan et al., 2021; Jiang et al., 2021; Li et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2021; Yan et al., 2021; Yin et al., 2021; Zhuang et al., 2021). Treatment for COVID-19 benefits from the rapid dissemination of evidence, if data for synthesizing gave evidence is continually compiled by systematic reviewers. This resulted in multiple systematic reviews with overlapping evidence, and each article was updated at the time of publication to include only one or two added studies . End users of research are prone to confusion and misdirection when there are few systematic reviews of comparable issues. Consequently, the purpose of performing an LSR is to supply direction in the form of a comprehensive and up-to-date review of the relevant literature. During this evaluation, extensive research (such as a comprehensive search of several databases) was carried out , with the use of analytical techniques (for example, the random effects model) found to be most proper for the evidence collected . instead of the fixed effect model). This LSR and meta-analyses will be updated quarterly with differences between each release brought to the attention of readers.

5. Observations and Recommendations for Future Research and Practice

Evidence suggests that adding herbal remedies to the usual treatment for COVID-19 patients offers significant advantages; however, the risks to significant consequences for the patient concerned are very uncertain and cannot be decided with certainty. Data surrounding the potentially harmful effects of using herbal medicine treatments is likewise fraught with uncertainty, due to inconsistent

reporting of safety outcomes. Treatments involving herbal remedies may be recommended after questions about their benefits and safety have been satisfactorily answered. In addition, there was a lack of consistency in outcome assessments throughout the included study. The primary results reported varied from study to study and included many results considered to be of little importance. Despite the many hurdles that COVID-19 clinical research must overcome, improving the quality of evidence requires ideal trial designs consisting of substantial sample sizes, randomization or blinding procedures, and outcome measures and proper reporting. As a result, future RCTs linked to herbal remedies for the treatment of COVID -19 stay a highly expected topic. These RCTs must be properly created.

6. Herbs and Related Products

Herbs and related products are also widely used by patients seeking traditional health care. All physicians, regardless of specialty or interest, take care of patients using products that are not prescribed or recommended. "Some herbs have been extensively studied, but little is known about others." ("Herbs as medicines - PubMed") How should a doctor respond when a patient asks for advice on the use of a particular herb? Similarly, how does a doctor decide whether a patient's symptoms are due to a "treatment"? This review attempts to answer these questions by examining related definitions, the history of herbs in medicine, the epidemiology and prevalence of herbal use, and related psychosocial issues.

While a full review of specific herbs is not possible in this setting (>20,000 herbal and related products are used in the United States),¹ the potential benefits and dangers of some of the more popular herbal products in use have been studied.

The earliest evidence of humans using plants for healing dates to the Neanderthal period. In the 16th century, botanical gardens were created to grow medicinal plants for medical schools. Herbal medicine practices flourished until the 17th century when it became more "scientific". Pharmacological drugs were preferred.

7. epidemiology

Estimates of the prevalence of herbal medicine use differ, with studies concluding that between 3% and 93% of the US population use herbs. The variability of these estimates is due to different descriptions of plants.

Internationally, botanical drug use is generally higher. For example, 70% of "Western" doctors in Japan prescribe campo drugs daily.¹¹ Eighty percent of the world's population rely primarily on traditional medicines for their health needs. It is certain that doctors care for patients who use herbs, and as discussed, this use can affect patient health issues and the effects of conventional treatments.

Individual costs and the costs of individual products can also be significant, although variable. An epidemiological study of human immunodeficiency virus-positive patients found that the average herbal user spends \$ 18 per month (range , \$0.175) on herbs. Individual products have variable costs depending on both the product and its source (home grown, imported, from a health food store or an herbalist).

8. Why Do People Use Herbal Medicines?

There are many reasons why patients turn to herbal treatments. The often-quoted "sense of control, a mental comfort that comes from taking action," helps explain why many people who take herbs have chronic or incurable diseases such as diabetes, cancer, arthritis, or AIDS. In such cases, they often believe that traditional medicine has failed them. When patients use home remedies for acute, often self-limiting conditions such as the common cold, sore throat, or bee sting, it is often because professional care is not at once available, is too laborious, costly, or time-consuming.

"Natural plant products are perceived to be healthier than manufactured medicines." ("Herbs as Medicines | Complementary and Alternative Medicine | JAMA ...") In addition, reports of adverse effects of traditional drugs are much higher in the non-traditional press than reports of herbal toxicity, in part because adverse effects monitoring mechanisms exist for conventional drugs. are drugs , while for self-treatment such data are more difficult to detect. Even doctors often dismiss

herbs as harmless placebos,¹⁰ and many consumers and doctors alike mistakenly believe that anything in pill form is approved by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA).

9. Dietary Supplement and Health Education

Due to the lack of quality control, safety and efficacy requirements, consumers cannot decide whether the active ingredients of a plant are in the product, whether the ingredient is bioavailable, whether the dosage is proper, whether it is in the next bottle they buy. Any herb or blend may vary from producer to producer and batch to batch; A plant that is toxic or non-therapeutic in one form or strength may be beneficial or harmful in a different preparation. The potency of various compounds is affected by growing conditions, storage, processing and preparation such that the potency of various products from the same plant can vary by 10,000 times. Producers use different methods to process the same plants; for example, the herb can be ground and pillled, or pharmaceutical methods can be used to extract the desired compound, assay composition, and make tablets of consistent strength.

Labels may be inaccurate or intentionally incorrect. The same common name can be applied to different plants proposed for different diseases. Some products labeled as ginseng also have mandrake (scopolamine) or cohosh (reserpine), due to the prohibitive cost of pure ginseng. Additives may be used but are listed on the labels; they can be the source of the therapeutic effect. Examples include steroids, nonsteroidal anti- inflammatory agents, prescription antibiotics, tranquilizers, and narcotics.

Misidentification of plants is possible, as is harvesting the wrong part of the plant. In New York, one case of belladonna poisoning was attributed to an herbal tea, and a similar misidentification resulted in digitalis poisoning from a mislabeled banana extract. Both events occurred because of an error in product labeling.

Heavy metals are often found in herbal medicines imported from foreign countries, as they are believed to aid the healing process even though they cannot be absorbed . On the other hand, the research literature has several explanations for cases of poisoning by lead, arsenic, cadmium,

copper, and mercury detected in herbal medicines imported from other countries. Another disadvantage with herbs bought from overseas vendors is that going with written instructions, if any, are often written in a language other than English.

10. Studies on Benefit and Risks

Controlled research on natural treatments is not financially practical.

(1) must do so and

(2) Because they are unable to patent the product to offset the estimated \$350 million in costs of proving a new drug to be effective and safe, there is little motivation for manufacturers to introduce randomized, placebo-controlled administration .

Such clinical trials are necessary to prove that a drug is effective. For a study to yield patentable and thus lucrative results, a unique extraction method or pharmaceutical dosage form must be developed alongside an entirely new drug. Any of these must be found as a direct result of conducting the research.

Despite these limitations, there is still some scientific research being conducted. Such studies often start in another country where funding restrictions are not as onerous as in a country where regulatory authorities need some basic scrutiny of a product's safety and efficacy.

11. Toxicity

It is important to know that all traditional medicines have the potential to cause toxicity in the body. On the other hand, unlike herbal medicines, traditional pharmaceuticals undergo clinical studies and post-approval monitoring that characterize these toxicities. This provides medical professionals with the facts necessary to weigh the risks of treatment against potential benefits. In addition to the components of the drug, the therapeutic window is showed, as well as the dose. As a result of strict quality controls, each tablet is the same as the others in terms of the ingredients it

has. Adverse reactions to herbal remedies are likely not to be found and reported as often as they should.

best approach for doctors to decide if an herb is the source of a patient's symptoms is to have a shelf reference in their office. Physicians should be familiar with some of the most common toxicities associated with herbal remedies.

Also, case reports can be searched for in published works, the remedy in question sent to a laboratory equipped to study a particular herb (toxicology laboratory should be consulted in university hospital settings). The FDA also provides users with up-to-date safety information about herbal products on its website (<http://www.fda.gov>). In cases of moderate toxicity, such as gastrointestinal upset or mildly elevated results in liver function tests, the treating physician may decide to drop herbal therapy to see if the patient's symptoms improve before deciding to try treatment again.

Little research has been done on interactions that can occur between controlled drugs and herbs; however, awareness of the potential side effects (as well as their therapeutic activities) of herbal medicines can be helpful in predicting drug interactions. For example, plants having cardiac glycosides have the potential to increase the effects of digoxin, and plants capable of causing diuresis to have the potential to increase the toxicity of digoxin by causing potassium loss. Herbs that can cause hypertension or hypotension may interact negatively with prescription antihypertensive medications; Herbs that are hypoglycemic can cause a patient with diabetes to lose control of their blood sugar levels. The metabolism of some herbs can be altered in a way that makes them incompatible with some prescription drugs. For example, eucalyptus can stimulate the production of microsomal liver enzymes⁵¹, while echinacea It is known that the flavonoids found in purpura reduce the activity of drug metabolizing enzymes such as cytochrome P-4503A4 and sulfotransferase .

Herbal treatment not only has the potential to be toxic but choosing an herbal remedy over a conventional treatment that has been shown to be effective can also be risky. A considerable number of oncologists met patients with early-stage tumors who opted for curative conventional therapy in favor of alternative treatments such as herbal remedies. After these herbal treatments

failed, patients returned to their oncologists with incurable metastatic disease. In fact, research has shown that patients who use herbs and other alternative medicines are more likely to drop conventional treatment when faced with an illness. This is especially true where traditional medicines could possibly help. Patients may also continue to develop harmful habits, such as smoking or drinking copious amounts of alcohol, in the belief that the herbal treatment they receive will protect against the negative effects of these activities.

The use of dietary supplements consisting of natural ingredients dates back thousands of years. The use of herbal supplements is becoming more common among consumers in the United States today. On the other hand, not everyone can receive help from them. The use of herbal supplements is still fraught with controversy, as the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and other regulatory authorities have not studied them in as much detail as they should.

12. Special Considerations for Herbal Medicines

Herbal remedies may be mistakenly considered completely safe because they are 'natural' products. This is not always true. Herbal remedies can produce adverse effects that can range from mild to severe, including :

- *allergic reactions and rashes*
- *asthma*
- *headache _*
- *nausea _*
- *vomiting*
- *diarrhea*

13. Detailed Description of the Intervention

Another weight reduction technique that can be used by those who are overweight or obese in addition to a weight loss diet, behavioral adjustments, and physical activity is the use of antiobesity

medications. Currently, obesity treatment requires the use of synthetic chemical drugs that often come with a high price tag and a host of undesirable side effects. As a result, patients and researchers are seeking alternative treatment approaches, including the use of herbal remedies and products, as safer and more effective ways to treat their condition. [9–11] Weight loss and prevention of future weight gain can be achieved with the aid of a wide variety of herbal remedies, including plant extracts and active ingredients separated from various herbs.

Most herbal medicines and their products have been researched with little clinical research; However, none have been considered a definitive answer for weight loss, and the mechanism of action of many of these herbal remedies is still a mystery.

14. Conclusion and Recommendations

Herbal medicines and products derived from them have the potential to lose weight through five different mechanisms. These mechanisms are suppression of appetite and reduction of energy intake, stimulation of thermogenesis and acceleration of metabolism, inhibition of pancreatic lipase activity and reduction of fat absorption, and reduction of lipogenesis and acceleration of lipolysis, respectively. The efficacy of herbal medicine as a treatment for obesity and metabolic syndrome has been investigated in several systematic studies in the past. As obesity has become an especially important problem in recent years, there is an urgent need for new systematic reviews of obesity, with particular emphasis on randomized clinical trials. Sensitivity analysis will be used to decide the effects of the potential for bias of the study on the most relevant results.

It is possible to lose weight and keep it off by making use of a wide variety of herbal remedies, which may include the use of plant extracts or active chemicals derived from various plants. The results of several preliminary studies suggest that herbal medicine may be an intervention that can control obesity at a lower cost than other treatments. In earlier systematic reviews, it was decided whether herbal therapy was effective in the treatment of metabolic syndrome and obesity as a treatment choice. The increasing number of randomized clinical trials conducted in recent years and the heterogeneity of their protocols prevented them from drawing firm conclusions about the

efficacy of herbal medicine, although some studies had excellent methodology . obesity treatment. Therefore, it would be reasonable to assume that there is a need for an updated, comprehensive and objective new systematic for the clinical efficacy and safety of herbal medicines in the treatment of obesity. This will supply the evidence base necessary for the development of future treatment recommendations. This systematic review will supply an in-depth overview as well as the latest analysis of the available evidence supporting the effectiveness of herbal remedies in the treatment of obesity. The findings of this study will be a guide in terms of patient treatment and health policy.

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